

ONLINE PROCESS MONITORING AND CONTROL BY DIELECTRIC SENSORS FOR A COMPOSITE MAIN SPAR FOR WIND TURBINE BLADES

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays in the wind turbine industry the enlargement of turbines enforces high demands on the manufacturing of wind turbine blades. Composites are used in different configurations like sandwich laminates to build the outer shape of the blade while full laminates are used to be the load carrying main spar. In this study an online monitoring scheme to determine viscosity and permeability for a composite main spar infusion is presented. During the manufacturing process, defects such as dry spots and pores can occur and lead to poor part quality. In this study, dielectric sensors are used to understand the infusion forced flow inside of a thick laminate up to 60mm. Additional experiments have been carried out to investigate the correlation between the sensors signal and the viscosity and to derive constitutive equations. The provided data and the derived permeabilities are integrated into a simulation model of a 2D cross section of the composite main spar. As a result, the real permeability can be identified. The knowledge of these parameters is one of the key aspects for a prediction of the resin flow and therefore for an improved process control.

1 INTRODUCTION

Various problems can occur in the manufacturing process of thick composite parts. Especially during the resin infusion, defects as dry spots and formation of pores not only indicate unstable, but also time-consuming and cost-intensive processes. The objective of this paper is to introduce a method to prevent these defects by an optimized process development scheme for main spars of rotor blades. As by now these rotor blades double their size every ten years, their construction represents a key example of processes where better materials and improved processes are strongly recommended [1]. In the course of this development, transparent glass fibers have been replaced by high tensile carbon fibers and new infusion concepts have been tested. Up to now, the substitution of a material or even a slight change in the process normally causes a large amount of trials to test the configuration.

Figure 1: IDEX-sensor (interdigital electrode) with/without a protective glass fiber mat.

This common experience-based approach comes to its limits, though. The intense need of time and material requires more knowledge-based process development and quality assurance. To realize stable processes, and increase energy and material efficiency, e.g. Brauner proposes a virtual process chain [2]. Brauner et.al. applied a sensor to measure the dielectric function and the temperature, depicted in figure 1. This sensor can be used at three different stages of the composite process chain: (I) Infusion (resin arrival and viscosity); (II) Curing (degree of cure [3]); (III) Structural Health Monitoring (moisture [4]). With this type of versatile sensor, the process can be controlled most effectively, and the number of embedded sensors can be optimally minimized.

2 APPROACH

In the present study, the infusion is investigated and simulated as part of a virtual process chain, see figure 2. This means certain input parameters, e.g. the fiber orientation, are known from a previous step and certain output parameters, e.g. defects, shall be given to the next element of the chain.

Figure 2: Virtual process chain for the production of fiber reinforced plastics by infusion technique.

These defects, such as dry spots and pores, are defined based on the method described below. Instead of conventional testing, all quantities shall be obtained by online monitoring using the implemented sensors only. The method itself is based on trials performed in advance and a resin flow simulation with the commercial software RTM-worx [5].

Two different parameters are online-monitored during infusion:

- (I) The permeability of the resin flow is determined in-situ.
- (II) The resin viscosity is derived from sensor data.

The infusion process for fiber reinforced plastics can be generally described as the flow of a fluid in porous media, which is modeled based on Darcy's Law [6]. Darcy developed this law in 1856 by observing water flowing through sand. He found that the velocity (\vec{v}) of the fluid is proportional to the pressure gradient (∇p). Darcy's Law is widely used for the modeling of resin flow – also most

commercial software are based on this approach. The proportionality factor for resin flow in fibrous media consists of the dry fibers permeability (K) divided by the resin viscosity μ :

$$\vec{v} = \frac{K}{\mu} \cdot \nabla \vec{p}. \quad (1)$$

These two process parameters (K and μ) being needed to describe the resin flow are monitored online (I-II).

2.1 Permeability.

The permeability describes the penetrability of the fibers for the resin. The factor permeability can be deduced from the above formula (1). Together with the continuity equation for flow processes an analytic solution can be derived and solved for K [7]. K has the form of a tensor which consists of the directional permeabilities K_x and K_y (for 2D).

Transferred to the online monitoring process, the velocity is needed in addition to the viscosity and the pressure gradient. Commonly, this information is derived by collecting pairs of variates

Figure 3: Determination of the permeability via equation (1) and the time difference between two sensor positions (with φ being the fibre volume content).

consisting place and time. Here, both types of sensors are applied to recognize the time when the resin arrives at the sensor position as shown in figure 3.

2.2 Viscosity

The viscosity of a fluid is a parameter of its resistance to deformation by shear stress. During the infusion process, the viscosity directly influences the flow velocity. Generally, the viscosity of resin depends on two factors: temperature and degree of cure. This functional correlation is well known in common models [8]. The central issue is that the degree of cure itself is again dependent on the temperature profile of the resin. For that reason, it is quite complicated to just model and calculate the real degree of cure online within the process. Thus, the viscosity is determined in-situ by an interdigital sensor (IDEX-sensor). This sensor is able to measure the dielectric function of the resin by quantifying the alignment of dipoles and migrating ions between two electric poles, which are under an alternating current. The measuring scheme is shown in figure 4 and can be found in detail in [9].

Figure 4: Functionality of the dielectric analysis: (a) pattern of an IDEX sensor, (b) alignment of the dipoles and ion migration, (c) phase-shifting of the alternating current. [9]

Part of the dielectric properties of a material is the ion viscosity, which is directly correlated to the dynamic viscosity. This dependence was verified in a series of experiments, where resin was cured under different constant temperatures. Representative results are shown in figure 5.

The parallel courses of curves indicate that the dynamic viscosity can be derived from the ion viscosity as long as a starting point is given, where both, the dynamic and the ion viscosity are known.

Figure 5: Correlation between the dynamic and ion viscosity of resin at 30°C and 40°C for five different trials.

In case of infusions, this point is right at the beginning where the resin system is just mixed together. The viscosity can be read from the technical data sheet. In table 1, all results are summarized. The starting point is given by the ion viscosity at a dynamic viscosity of $1 \text{ Pa} \cdot \text{s}$.

Temperature	c(T)	Log ion viscosity at $1 \text{ Pa} \cdot \text{s}$	Partial regression line
30°C	0.326	8.74 Ohm cm	$\text{Ion viscosity} = 0.326 \ln(\mu) + 8.74 \text{ Ohm cm}$
35°C	0.364	8.70 Ohm cm	$\text{Ion viscosity} = 0.364 \ln(\mu) + 8.70 \text{ Ohm cm}$
40°C	0.407	8.91 Ohm cm	$\text{Ion viscosity} = 0.407 \ln(\mu) + 8.91 \text{ Ohm cm}$

Table 1: Regression curves for the correlation between the dynamic and ion viscosity at different temperatures.

2.3 Defects

To reach a point where the position of a pore can be determined by the sensor data, some modeling of the relation between the resin flow velocity and the formation of pores has to be done. Two different causes of pore formation are investigated. (1) Air entrapment due to a deformed flow front, and (2) Air entrapment due to a very slow or very fast flow front, as shown in figure 6 and 7.

Figure 6: Capillary flow is dominant: formation of macro pores.

The first type where capillary flow is dominant can be monitored by the above mentioned approach to localize the flow front. The second type dominated by inter tow flow indicates a correlation between the resin velocity and the formation of macro or micro pores. Generally, higher resin velocities create micro pores while lower velocities tend to create macro pores. Ruiz et.al. propose a minimum existing at a medium resin velocity \vec{v}^* [10]. This \vec{v}^* has to be determined for every combination of material and layup individually.

Figure 7: Inter tow flow is dominant: formation of micro pores.

3 RESULTS

The aim for the dielectric sensor is to identify the process parameters permeability and viscosity. The infusion setup for the experiment is displayed in figure 8. During the trials, the resin flow direction is always perpendicular to the fiber direction to simulate the infusion concept of a main spar for a rotor blade. Dealing with real main spars of up to 90 meters, only a cross section is observed and simulated. The related loss of information is negligible because the resin flow in fiber direction is nearly zero.

Figure 8: Schematic vacuum setup for a line infusion.

Thus, the simulation can be done much faster and is applicable for an online optimization scheme to influence the process. The implemented dielectric sensors are placed on the middle layer. If a transparent tooling is used the resin flow can be observed on three planes through the thickness direction of the laminate.

Figure 9: Schematic 2D cross section of the infusion setup with sensor positions.

Two concepts, described in the paragraphs 'permeability' and 'viscosity', are used as follows. The permeability can either be determined directly from the sensor and observation data. Or it is identified by an optimization scheme with a resin flow simulation software which makes use of the viscosity data from the dielectric sensors. The advantage of using the software is that both directions of the permeability K_x and K_y can be identified simultaneously. The infusion setup is shown in figure 9 and 10.

Figure 10: Dielectric sensors on the middle layer.

In all, the infusion is running for about 120 minutes with a typical epoxy resin¹ for rotor blades and 60 layers unidirectional NCF². The result of the IDEX sensors is shown in figure 11.

Top layer	time [min]	0	2	5	10	17	25	38	51	64	76	97	107	125
	flow length [mm]	150	167	176	183	191	197	206	216	230	241	261	272	280
middle layer	time [min]	0	17	18	21	41								
	flow length [mm]	0	50	140	230	320								
bottom layer	time [min]	0	3	7	12	19	27	36	51	80	125			
	flow length [mm]	300	326	336	344	354	361	367	374	382	388			

Table 2: Flow lengths for the resin infusion with dielectric sensors along the top, middle and bottom layer.

Four out of five sensors were impregnated during this experiment. The advantage in not filling the part completely is that the shape of the flow front can be easily compared with the predicted shape from the resin flow simulation afterwards. The graphs in figure 11 show the impregnation time of the four sensors at 17, 18, 21 and 41 minutes after the beginning of the infusion. For the top and bottom layer, the results are summarized in table 2.

Now, the viscosity can be directly derived from the sensor data displayed in figure 11. The ion viscosity ranges from $7 - 7.3 \text{ Ohm} \cdot \text{cm}$. The temperature is held constant at 30°C , so the first row of table 1 is solved for the dynamic viscosity

$$\mu = e^{\zeta - \zeta_1 / 0.326}. \quad (2)$$

¹ EPIKOTE™ Resin MGS® RIMR035c with EPIKURE™ Curing Agent MGS® RIMH037

² unidirectional carbon NCF, surface weight: 620 g/m², stockinet stitch, 50k tows

Figure 11: Ion and dynamic viscosity over time in the infusion with 60 layers carbon NCF.

Where ζ is the ion viscosity and ζ_1 is the ion viscosity at a respective dynamic viscosity of $1 Pa \cdot s$. Based on the known combination of dynamic and ion viscosity at the beginning of the infusion, the value for ζ_1 can be determined [11]:

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_{start} &= 0.175 Pa \cdot s, \\ \zeta_{0.175} &= 7 Ohm \cdot cm, \\ \Rightarrow \zeta_1 &= 7 Ohm \cdot cm - 0.326 \cdot \ln(0.175) = 7.57 Ohm \cdot cm. \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

This gives the possibility to calculate the maximum viscosity

$$\mu_{max} = e^{7.25-7.57/0.326} = 0.374 Pa \cdot s \quad (4)$$

in the infusion after 120 minutes. In figure 11, the viscosity development and the ion viscosity are plotted over the course of the infusion.

sensor	t_1 [s]	t_2 [s]	distance[m]	Viscosity[Pa · s]	$K = \frac{\varphi \cdot \mu \cdot \Delta l^2}{2 \cdot \Delta p \cdot (t_2 - t_1)}$	direction
1	0	1050	0.18	$\mu_{525s} = 0.174$	$1.62 \cdot 10^{-13} m^2$	K_y
2	0	1080	0.18	$\mu_{540s} = 0.175$	$1.58 \cdot 10^{-13} m^2$	K_y
3	0	1260	0.18	$\mu_{630s} = 0.176$	$1.36 \cdot 10^{-13} m^2$	K_y
4	1260	2490	0.02	$\mu_{1875s} = 0.193$	$1.88 \cdot 10^{-13} m^2$	K_x

Table 3: Estimation for the permeability values in x- and y-direction with the scheme, presented in figure 3.

The permeability is derived from the resin arrival at the sensors, see table 3. Afterwards, this data is used as an initial value for the optimization scheme with the resin infusion software.

The calculation for the first three sensors is based on the fact that the resin flows directly from beneath the infusion setup to the sensors. For the fourth sensor, the resin flows horizontally from the last point of the flow media. Here, the flow path changes to x-direction. The fiber volume of 58% content was determined according to the standard DIN EN 2564 and the calculation was performed with a standard atmosphere of 101325 Pa and a vacuum pressure of 5000 Pa.

The optimization is performed by a trial-and-error attempt with the resin flow software RTM-worx [12]. Positions for seven key points (KP1-KP7) plus the four sensors (S1-S4) are defined in table 2 (in italic font). These shall be reached as exactly as possible with the viscosity trend given by the sensor data.

The course of the simulation for the part (figure 9) is shown in figure 12. The ideal combination of the permeabilities in x - and y -direction is matched with $K_x = 1,27 \cdot 10^{-12}m^2$ and $K_y = 1,04 \cdot 10^{-13}m^2$. The value for K_y is well predicted by the estimation. The slight difference is probably caused by the increasing viscosity which cannot be included in the permeability equation, see table 3. The estimated value for K_x is not very accurate. This can be explained by the sensor position and the course of the flow front. It is very difficult to extract real flow in x -direction. This is also one of the main reasons to perform the optimization. Almost every experiment includes at least two directions of resin flow, which cannot be separated easily.

Figure 12: Course of the resin flow simulation at three time steps.

Three important steps are presented in figure 12: the situation when the two flow fronts from the top and the bottom infusion lines merge in the middle air can be entrapped (20 minutes). The same problem can occur, when the resin emerges to the top boundary of the part on a large area (41 minutes). The state of the infusion after 125 minutes shows the end of the experiment.

4 OUTLOOK

The aim of this study was to generate an optimized process development scheme to prevent dry spots and formation of pores during an infusion process. As a reference part a composite main spar for rotor blades was chosen. Furthermore the method was based on sensorial input by interdigital electrodes (IDEX-sensors). These sensors measure the dielectric properties of the resin, and can be used to determine the permeability and viscosity in-situ.

Figure 13: Flow front control by changing the temperature in different heating zones to control the viscosity of the resin.

It was shown that, with little effort, it is possible to reconstruct all process parameters to model the infusion process. The viscosity can be directly derived from the sensor data and used as an input parameter for the resin flow simulation. With few information about the resin flow front the simulation software can determine the permeability in an optimization scheme. With this knowledge, it is possible to predict further resin flow.

The next step from process monitoring to process control would be to couple the sensor-evaluation part with an actuator. E.g. a heated tool can directly influence the viscosity in the process and can therefore change the course of an infusion, see figure 13.

Further applications, such as using the sensor over a wider span of the virtual process chain, are possible. But, therefore the sensor has to stay inside the laminate and needs to be miniaturized. Reducing the influence on the mechanical properties of the component could be a main part of future research.

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